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“EDUCATION: A MILESTONE EVERYONE DESERVES”

An overrated quotation says that “Education is the key to success.” Although it is a true statement, it is overly used by many but despite the quantity of people around the world who know about this quotation, many were able to overshadow the challenges our world faces in making quality education system that is accessible for everyone. The year 2030 is fast approaching, this is the year that the 17 Sustainable Development Goals adopted by the United Nations are intended to be achieved where quality education is also considered as priority being the SDG no. 4. However, there are people around the world who are still struggling to have access to it due to certain circumstances: poverty, existing wars, and inability to provide enough school facilities, and more. For the next 5 years, may the world leaders maximize their efforts for these SDGs to be achieved because education is more than just going to school every day, it is a process of empowering individuals and building opportunities for better and comfortable life in the future, while these adds up to the factuality of the quotation mentioned above, education must be more than just a privilege, it is a human right that everyone must have, yet not everyone has the same access to it.

In all aspects of a person’s life, having proper education can be the root of majority the knowledge a person can reach. The first step is always the hardest part, every child’s first day of school was surely full of uncertainty, doubt, and fear, but everyone went through this and overcame the feelings of being naïve at an early age. As time passed by, we learned to perceive these as opportunities to gain experience and discover. Other children were able to figure out their strengths and weaknesses, likes and dislikes, while others enhanced their talents, and others uncovered things they never thought of. These little discoveries deepen their self-awareness and lead them to prove their identity and own principles in life, which are all reflected in how they socialize and connect with their surroundings. On a deeper sense, education is also the foundation of our future careers. Aside from personal development, pursuing their dreams is one of their reasons for going to school. It is a preparatory stage for more serious roles, it is where they are taught to be prepared for the challenges of the competitive and fast-paced world, where they should learn to work under pressure, be flexible, and manage their time effectively and properly. In other words, education is an effective tool for everyone to achieve their dreams and secure success. Moreover, educators also teach students to be a responsible citizen in the future. They say, “no man is an island.” It means that people should be conscious of their actions because other members of the community will be affected. Learning this at school will not only enable one person to be responsible but also learn the essence of having empathy and caring for others.

Furthermore, learning to vote wisely, caring for the environment, and simply being kind to others are all forms of responsible citizenship. To sum it all up, personal development, career security, and responsible citizenship boil down to highlight how important it is to have access to education, failing not to have it will result in different problems in the future such as financial insecurity, unemployment, and self-insecurity.

Education is more than just a journey of reaching knowledge and securing employment, it is a human right that everyone deserves to have. International organizations like United Nations advocate education to be accessible. Aside from them, everyone must understand that proper education must be fought, especially in the first stages of one's life to allow them to build the foundation of their maturity and participation as responsible citizen of the community. Education as a human right helped people to understand how the world works, how to make informed decisions, and how to build a secure future for everyone who has access to it. Otherwise, opportunities for them will be limited and personal freedom can be restricted due to inability to have it.

Schools are the place where this milestone of every individual can be reached, while education as a milestone is for generality, education has specific aspects being improved at various stages. Every child's first achievement can be achieved in primary school, while they can grow as independent individual during high school, and tertiary level will give them an overview of their professional career in the future. It is obviously a step-by-step process where it challenges other parts of the child to grow and adapt to the changes at every stage. Therefore, if these stages were not met by someone in their entire life, it can result them not having stability in the future. Yet even though it is considered as a human right, 250 million children around the world continue to face the same struggles of not having access to education due to different challenges such as social, cultural, and financial. Although our leaders are doing their best to make continuous progress towards education it is undeniable that they need extra effort to fulfill education across the world.

Education is truly the milestone that everyone deserves because it is a journey to achieve independence, opportunities, and understating. It is a right that belongs to everyone regardless of who they are. But sadly, 250 million children around the world are deprived of education. For us to build a world where equality radiates for everyone even to those who are in isolated places, everyone must be encouraged to uplift this right and to ensure that it is not just promised but provided by our leaders. For every child who steps into the classroom takes a powerful step towards the empowered version of themselves carrying their potential. When the day comes that education can be truly accessible for everyone, the greatness of our world will be uncovered and competence, responsible citizenship will be shared all throughout the community and financial security will be attained to finally eliminate hunger, unemployment, and self-insecurity. Indeed, education is not just a privilege but a milestone everyone deserves, it should be out beginning, not a barrier.

